

DEVELOPMENT AND MANUFACTURING OF A CONFORMABLE CFRP TANK DEMONSTRATOR WITH TENSION-STRUT-REINFORCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the manufacturing and testing of conformable carbon fiber-reinforced polymer tanks with integrated continuous fiber-reinforced tension struts for hydrogen storage applications. Two demonstrator tanks were manufactured using 3D-printed core structures combined with wet filament winding and hand lay-up processes. While the concept demonstrated mechanical integrity under hydrostatic loading, leakage at the interface between the CFRP and aluminum boss, as well as poor laminate compaction in flat regions, revealed existing challenges. The manual forming of the strut ends was time-consuming and resulted in high variability in joint strength. These results highlight the potential of strut reinforcement while emphasizing the need for improved laminate compaction and enhanced strut-wall connection to enable practical applications of conformable composite tanks.

1 MOTIVATION AND BACKGROUND

As climate change progresses, sustainable mobility is becoming increasingly important. In the passenger car sector, battery electric vehicles (BEVs) have become the dominant form of locally emission-free mobility [1–3]. Nevertheless, some manufacturers are additionally pursuing hydrogen-powered fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEVs) to provide an alternative to BEVs [4, 5]. Due to the low production volumes, these vehicles are expensive, which represents a key barrier to broader consumer adoption [3, 6]. A cost-reduction approach is to use the same vehicle architecture for both BEVs and FCEVs. To use the skateboard platform, which is common for BEVs, in FCEVs, the hydrogen storage system must be integrated into a flat installation space in the vehicle underbody [7, 8]. Hydrogen pressure vessels on the market have a cylindrical geometry and are therefore not well suited to this installation space [7].

One approach to using the volume more efficiently for hydrogen storage is to use conformable tanks, which are adapted to the cuboid design space [7]. However, pressure vessels that deviate from a cylindrical or spherical geometry are subject to high bending forces in the vessel walls [11]. This makes it necessary to integrate reinforcing elements such as struts or ribs to counteract these forces. Several approaches for conformable composite tanks can be found in literature [7, 8, 11–13]. A major challenge is the connection of the reinforcing elements (struts, ribs, etc.) to the tank wall, as very high forces have to be transmitted in this area [11, 14].

This work presents a manufacturing process for conformable CFRP tanks with inner tension-strut reinforcement. The main aim is to investigate the feasibility of the presented concept through the development, fabrication, and testing of two tank demonstrators.

2 CONCEPT AND DESIGN

This chapter outlines the overall concept for a conformable CFRP tank with tension-strut-reinforcement, including the design of the winding core and boss elements, the integration strategy for the struts, the composite layup definition, and the materials for demonstrator manufacturing.

2.1 Manufacturing concept

The basic manufacturing concept was presented in a previous contribution at ECCM20 [15] and is briefly summarized here for completeness.

The concept consists of four main steps, as shown in Figure 1. In the first step, a winding core with integrated continuous fiber-reinforced struts is prepared. The struts, which have a thermoplastic (TP) matrix, are positioned such that both ends protrude beyond the surface of the core. In the second step, the tank wall is formed using the wet winding process. During the deposition of the impregnated fibers on the winding core, the ends of the struts pierce the rovings, resulting in a semi-finished product with an uncured composite laminate in which the end sections of the struts protrude from the outer surface of the laminate. In the third manufacturing step, the end portions of the TP-CFRP struts are formed into a flat geometry using heat. In the final step, an outer composite laminate is formed using the filament winding process to cover the reshaped ends of the struts.

Figure 1: Overview of the manufacturing steps for the conformable CFRP tank with integrated tension struts [15].

The presented manufacturing concept demonstrates promising potential for the fabrication of conformable CFRP tanks with integrated tension struts. Compared to designs based on steel, the CFRP approach offers superior lightweight potential [14, 16]. Furthermore, the use of filament winding, a well-established process in pressure vessel manufacturing, supports scalability, as suitable equipment is already widely available in industry. An important aspect of the concept is the strut integration strategy, which is intended to allow efficient load transfer from the struts into the laminate along the fiber direction. In the configuration shown in Figure 1, a 3D-printed skeleton structure serves as a winding core. However, the concept is equally applicable to Type IV tanks, where a polymer liner with channels for the struts could fulfill this role. As such liners are currently not commercially available, the demonstrators presented in this study utilize a 3D-printed skeleton structure.

2.2 Design of winding core and boss element

The winding core for the demonstrators was designed using Catia V5 and is depicted in Figure 2. The core features a hexagonal structure, designed for 3D-printing without the need for additional support material between the hexagons. It includes holes at the intersection points for the struts, as well as

recesses to enable adhesive application during strut insertion. The core dimensions are 426 mm × 290 mm × 80 mm. The strut spacing was defined as a parameter, allowing the number of struts to be easily varied during the tank design process. Additionally, the winding core includes a recessed area for bonding the boss element, ensuring its precise positioning during assembly.

Figure 2: CAD design of the winding core.

The boss element and key dimensions are shown in Figure 3. It should be noted that the structural design of the boss was not focus of this project. Therefore, only an approximate design was created without detailed analyses, such as stiffness evaluation.

Figure 3: Boss element for conformable tank demonstrators and main dimensions in mm.

2.3 Strut integration and anchoring strategy

Comprehensive investigations to improve the strut connection were carried out. The general approach is shown in Figure 4. Parts of these investigations have been published in Gleis et al. [17]. As these investigations are not the focus of this publication, they are not discussed in further detail. From preliminary studies, a length of 4 mm for the reshaped strut end, combined with the application of thickened resin after bending of the struts was found to provide good connection strength between the struts and the tank wall.

For the building of the demonstrators, the thermal forming of the strut heads was conducted manually using a modified soldering iron. A conservative value of 1.5 kN was assumed for the transferable load between each strut and the tank wall for the definition of the strut spacing. This assumption accounts for the differing conditions during demonstrator manufacturing, which are less controlled compared to the laboratory environment during the parameter study.

Figure 4: Approach for improving the connection between the struts and the laminate of the tank wall.

2.4 Composite layup and strut configuration

For the fabrication of the demonstrator tanks, design parameters such as the number of composite layers, the stacking sequence and the number and spacing of the struts had to be determined. It should be noted that detailed structural design was not the focus of this work. The following procedure was used as a pragmatic approach to define the key design parameters. A burst pressure of 100 bar was defined as the design target. Since the objective of the project was to investigate the strut integration concept at demonstrator level, the design parameters were selected so that the laminate of the tank wall was oversized and the strut spacing served as the critical design parameter. The aim was to ensure that during burst testing, failure would occur at the strut connection rather than in the laminate.

Strut spacing

A simplified one-eighth model of the tank was simulated in Abaqus to define a reasonable strut spacing for the demonstrator. The strut spacing was adapted in the model to achieve a maximum stress of 361 MPa in the struts in fiber direction. With the strut diameter of 2.3 mm, this corresponds to the value of 1.5 kN assumed in Section 2.3 for the pull-out strength of the strut-wall connection and resulted in a strut spacing of 12 mm in the simulation. Since the struts are arranged in a square pattern in the Abaqus model and hexagonally in the core structure of the demonstrators (due to 3D-printing constraints), the spacing was adjusted to achieve a comparable reinforcement density, resulting in 10 mm spacing distance.

Composite Layup

As current winding software cannot generate winding paths for non-rotationally symmetric geometries such as the conformable tank demonstrators, a combined approach of filament winding and hand layup was employed for the tank wall. Layers oriented at 0° and 90° were realized through circumferential winding, while $\pm 45^\circ$ layers, as well as patches on the corners and sides of the demonstrators, were applied by hand layup. A schematic illustration of the composite layup approach and the used patches is shown in Figure 5.

The number of layers was set at a total of 16, with four repetitions of the sequence $0^\circ/90^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ$. Before placing each 0° layer, the corners of the tank were reinforced by hand lamination, and before each 90° layer, the side patches were applied. For the 0° layers, a manufacturing aid (shown in Figure 6, right) was used to wind over the boss elements.

As described above, the aim was to over-dimension the tank wall deliberately so that failure in the burst test occurs at the strut connection and not in the laminate. To verify the selected layup, the Abaqus model mentioned above was used to simulate the tank wall with 16 layers according to the specified orientations. The maximum stress in the fiber direction and the maximum shear stress were evaluated for each layer to ensure that these values were within a non-critical range for CFRP.

Figure 5: Schematic illustration of the layup strategy combining filament winding and hand layup for the conformable tank wall.

2.5 Materials

All the materials used for the manufacturing of the demonstrators, their specific designations, and the relevant manufacturing steps are listed in Table 1. Figure 6 shows the prepared fiber patches on the left. The conical strut caps and the 0° winding aid (middle and right) were 3D-printed using SLA resin. Two different resin systems were used for the two demonstrators, which required different 3D-printing filaments. For the demonstrator manufactured with the Araldite LY1135-1/917/960 resin system, PA6-CF was selected for the core structure due to its higher thermal resistance.

Material	Trade name	Manufacturing steps
Carbon fiber roving	Toray T700S-24K-50C	Filament winding of 90° and 0° layers
UD Non-crimp fabric (NCF)	SGL Sigratex® C U170-0/ST-E214/10g	Hand laminated edge and side patches
±45° NCF	Saertex ±45° 256 g/m ²	Patches for hand laminating of ±45° layers
Struts	SGL CF/PA6 struts (prototype material)	Reinforcing strut with carbon fiber d = 2.3 mm used for both demonstrators
Resin system for 1st demonstrator	SikaBiresin® CR80/CH10	Wet winding and hand lamination of 1st demonstrator
Resin system for 2nd demonstrator	Huntsman Araldite LY1135-1/917/960-1	Wet winding and hand lamination of 2nd demonstrator
3D-printing filament PETG	Polymaker PolyLite PETG	3D-printing of core structure for first demonstrator
3D-printing filament CF-PA11	Polymaker PolyMide PA6-CF	3D-printing of core structure for second demonstrator
SLA printing resin	Anycubic standard resin	Printing of manufacturing aid for 0° layers and strut caps
Adhesive	Scotch-Weld™ DP 490	Assembly of core structure, fixation of the struts in the core structure
Thixotropic agent	Evonik AEROSIL® 380	Viscosity increase of neat resin applied after strut forming
2K Silicone	SilikonFabrik SF00 - RTV2	Implementation of silicone layer into the 2nd demonstrator as an attempt to seal it

Table 1: Materials used for the manufacturing of the demonstrator tanks.

Figure 6: Prepared fiber patches (left) and 3D-printed strut caps (middle) and manufacturing aid for 0° layers (right).

3 MANUFACTURING OF THE DEMONSTRATORS

This chapter describes the manufacturing process of the demonstrator tanks, including the preparation of the winding cores with integrated struts, the combined filament winding and hand lay-up process, the anchoring of the strut ends, and the vacuum-assisted curing procedure.

3.1 Preparation of winding cores

The core structure of the demonstrators is fabricated in four individual segments using a fused deposition modeling (FDM) process on a Prusa i3 MK3S+ printer. After printing, the segments are assembled using a 2K epoxy adhesive (Scotch-Weld™ DP 490). Two different filament materials were used for the core structures of the two demonstrators: PETG and PA6-CF. The choice was based on the requirements of the respective resin systems, which necessitate different curing temperatures. PA6-CF offers a higher heat deflection temperature, while PETG is easier to process during printing. Figure 7 shows the printing process for a single segment and the four segments prior to assembly.

Figure 7: 3D-printing of a core segment (left) and the four segments prior to adhesive assembly (right).

The aluminum boss elements were adhesively bonded to the core structure using the aforementioned adhesive. As structural reinforcements, continuous fiber-reinforced tension struts were integrated into the conformable tank demonstrators. Prior to their insertion into the core structure, the struts were dried, cleaned with isopropanol, and trimmed to a uniform length. Each strut was individually bonded to the core structure using the DP490 adhesive, as shown in Figure 8. To facilitate piercing of the strut ends through the fiber layers during filament winding and hand lamination, conical strut caps with pointed ends were manually attached (Figure 8, right). The preparation of the core structure was very time-consuming due to the significant manual labor involved, such as the adhesive joining of 564 struts.

Figure 8: Insertion of continuous fiber-reinforced tension struts into the core structure with adhesive (left) and attachment of conical strut caps (right).

3.2 Filament winding and hand lay-up process

A total of 16 layers, consisting of four repetitions of the sequence $0^\circ/90^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ$, was applied. Before each 0° layer, the tank's corners were reinforced by hand lamination and before each 90° layer, the side patches were placed. After the first 0° and 90° layers, an intermediate curing step was implemented to prevent deformation of the 3D-printed core under thermal and mechanical process loads e.g. during strut forming.

For the circumferential layers in 0° and 90° direction, the wet filament winding process, shown in Figure 9, was applied. The fiber tension during winding was set to 10 N, and the winding paths were generated using CADWIND. As a workaround for the non-rotationally symmetric geometry of the conformable tank, cylindrical mandrels were modeled in CADWIND with equivalent circumferences to the core geometry in the respective 0° and 90° winding directions. The bandwidth was defined as 5.5 mm in the winding software. To enable winding in the 0° direction despite the presence of the boss element, a custom manufacturing aid was employed, as shown in Figure 9.

During winding, several practical challenges arose. In some cases, strut caps detached from the ends of the tension struts and had to be manually removed from the laminate, requiring an interruption of the winding process. Furthermore, due to the presence of the protruding strut ends, the rovings occasionally failed to deposit fully onto the surface of the mandrel and had to be manually pushed down. Winding across the boss element in the 0° direction using the manufacturing aid caused local deviations from the intended fiber alignment along the tank's longitudinal axis. Filament winding was chosen for these layers because it enables full 0° wrapping of the boss element and, compared to hand lamination, reduces the risk of layer detachment and shifting after placement.

Figure 9: Wet filament winding setup for circumferential layers: 90° (left) and 0° (right). A custom manufacturing aid was used in 0° to enable fiber deposition across the boss element.

The application of the prepared fiber patches by hand lamination is shown in Figure 10. For each $\pm 45^\circ$ NCF layer, two patches were applied: one on the top and one on the bottom of the tank, overlapping

along the curved sides. A brush was used to push the $\pm 45^\circ$ NCF down onto the mandrel surface along the struts. The patches applied along the sides of the demonstrators (see Figure 10, middle) are oriented in the 0° direction and were positioned so that the strut rows adjacent to the curved sides pierced each patch alternately from the top and bottom. To cover each of the four corners of the tank, six patches (shown in Figure 6) were placed side-by-side, as illustrated on the right in Figure 10. During the layup process, several issues arose due to insufficient fixation of the fiber patches. The lack of tension complicated accurate positioning, leading to patch movement and wrinkle formation during vacuum compaction.

Figure 10: Hand lamination process of $\pm 45^\circ$ NCF layers (left), 0° patches along the sides (middle), and coverage of the curved shoulders (left).

3.3 Anchoring of strut ends

The thermal forming of the strut ends was performed after the 12th layer. The struts, including the caps, were first trimmed with pliers, leaving 4 mm protruding. The remaining ends were flattened directly on the uncured laminate using a soldering iron with a flat tip. The intermediate state, with some strut ends already formed and the remaining ones trimmed, is shown in Figure 11 (left). Due to the high number of struts and the limited ability to form them in parallel at this early development stage, the manual forming process was very time-consuming. Approximately four hours were required for two people to complete the thermal forming on one demonstrator. To improve the mechanical performance of the strut–laminate interface, a layer of neat epoxy resin, shown in Figure 11 (right), mixed with 4 wt-% thixotropic agent (Aerosil 380) was applied. A 90° layer was immediately wound over the area to prevent resin runoff. The remaining layers were then applied according to the defined sequence.

Figure 11: Trimmed and formed strut ends (left) and resin application with thixotropic agent (right).

3.4 Vacuum-assisted curing process

To prepare the vacuum setup, a perforated release film was stretched over the wet laminate, followed by the application of breather fabric and vacuum film. Curing was performed under a vacuum of 400 mbar (absolute pressure). Cure cycles were resin-dependent: CR80-10 was cured for 10 hours at room temperature, while Araldite LY 1135-1/917/960 was cured for 4 hours at 80°C , followed by 6 hours at 120°C . The vacuum setup and the final demonstrators after curing are shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Vacuum setup (left) and final demonstrators after curing (right).

4 TESTING AND EVALUATION OF THE DEMONSTRATORS

4.1 Hydrostatic burst testing and leakage analysis

Hydrostatic burst tests were conducted on both demonstrators but had to be terminated early due to premature leakage. The tank manufactured with CR80-10 resin exhibited leakage at 80 bar, while the one using Araldite LY 1135-1/917/960 showed leakage at 30 bar. A follow-up test with compressed air and leak detection spray was performed to locate the leaks. In both cases, leakage occurred at the interface between the composite structure and the boss elements (see Figure 13, right). Figure 13 (left) shows one of the demonstrators in the burst test chamber.

Figure 13: Left: Demonstrator in hydrostatic burst chamber. Middle and right: Leak detection at the composite–boss interface using compressed air and leak detection spray.

4.2 Mass and volume

The two demonstrators had masses of 5.86 kg (Demonstrator 1, CR80-10) and 6.35 kg (Demonstrator 2, Araldite 1135/917/960) and an internal volume of 7.7 L. Assuming a design pressure of 100 bar and a safety factor of 2, this corresponds to a theoretical hydrogen capacity of 32 g, resulting in a gravimetric efficiency of 0.50-0.55%. In a dissertation by Ruf [16], a gravimetric efficiency of 5.9% was reported for a conformable tension-strut-reinforced Type IV tank. However, this value is based on simulation results and does not represent a demonstrator at technical scale. The low gravimetric efficiency observed here is partly due to the deliberate overdimensioning of the tank wall and manufacturing challenges leading to a relatively low fiber volume content. This result further highlights the early development stage and low technology readiness level (TRL) of the presented concept.

4.3 Supplementary inspection of laminate and strut connections

To gain further insight into the manufacturing process and investigate the demonstrators in more detail, both tanks were cut into quarters and samples were taken for microscopy and mechanical testing of the strut connections. Cross-sectional images revealed very high porosity and low fiber volume content, especially in the flat sections where the struts are integrated. In the boss area, the composite laminate detached from the aluminum surface during cutting, confirming insufficient bonding at the interface. A neat resin layer was observed on the tank side that faced downward during curing, likely due to gravity-induced flow. The effect was more distinct in the demonstrator manufactured with the

Araldite LY1135-1/917/960 resin system, as can be seen in Figure 14, middle. A cross-sectional image, as well as cut sections from both demonstrators are shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Cut sections of demonstrators made with CR80-10 (left) and Araldite 1135/917/960 (middle), and a microscopy image of a strut–laminate interface (right).

Mechanical pull-out tests were performed on a total of 57 samples taken from different sections of each demonstrator to investigate the strength of the joint between the strut and the tank wall. The tests showed an average pull-out force of 1.7 kN for both tanks. However, as already observed in previous studies of the strut connection [17], the results showed considerable scatter (± 0.4 kN), which is a known challenge for this concept.

5 DISCUSSION AND LESSONS LEARNED

The demonstrators provided valuable insights into the performance and manufacturability of the strut-reinforced conformable tank concept. Key aspects are summarized below.

Promising outcomes:

The integration of struts into the tank wall was successful in principle. The strut-wall connection withstood the forces expected from coupon-level testing and did not show mechanical failure during hydrostatic loading. In one of the demonstrators, no rupture occurred at 80% of the design pressure (i.e. 80 bar), indicating sufficient mechanical integrity of the strut anchorage. The test was aborted due to leakage, not structural failure.

Identified challenges:

A critical issue was leakage at the interface between the composite structure and the aluminum boss element. The lack of adhesive bonding and the mismatch in thermal expansion between aluminum and CFRP likely contributed to poor bonding, particularly during curing and cool-down of the demonstrator manufactured with the resin system Araldite 1135/917/960. Leakage occurred in both demonstrators: the one cured at 120 °C leaked at 30 bar, and the room-temperature cured one at 80 bar. This suggests that thermal effects may intensify the problem but are not the sole cause. The boss design further limited bonding strength due to the narrow contact area in the center. Local detachment of the laminate from the boss during cutting confirmed insufficient adhesion at the CFRP-boss interface.

Another major challenge was the laminate quality in the flat sections where the struts were integrated. Microscopy revealed severe porosity, attributed to inadequate compaction during winding. In filament winding, compaction relies on fiber tension combined with a convex surface. On flat surfaces, fiber tension does not result in compaction pressure. The presence of the protruding struts prevented the use of compaction rollers and intermediate vacuum consolidation steps. For future investigations, the struts could be inserted after winding to enable better compaction through suitable consolidation methods. However, inserting the struts after laminating introduces additional challenges. Besides the poor compaction, a resin layer was observed on the side of the tank that was positioned at the bottom during curing, which could in the future be prevented by rotating the tank during the curing process (compare Figure 14, middle).

The thermal forming of the strut ends was performed manually and lacked process control, resulting in significant scatter in the measured pull-out strength values. Additionally, the forming process, along

with steps such as inserting and bonding the struts to the winding core and trimming them prior to forming, proved to be highly labor-intensive and time-consuming when carried out manually.

Interpretation and concept evaluation:

From a structural standpoint, the strut-wall connection does not fully utilize the material potential. While the used PA6/CF struts have an average tensile strength of 986 MPa [17], corresponding to 4.1 kN, the strut-wall connection in the demonstrators reached only 1.7 kN on average, resulting in a connection efficiency of 41%. According to calculations by Gleis et al. [17], a 700 bar tank with 100% connection efficiency would require a strut spacing of 5.49 mm. This spacing poses significant manufacturing challenges but remains theoretically feasible given the 4 mm formed strut length used in the demonstrators. However, for the concept to achieve practical viability, the connection strength must be significantly increased. Under more controlled laboratory conditions, 2.1 kN has already been achieved, though further improvements are necessary.

From a manufacturing perspective, the current process is highly complex and involves numerous additional steps compared to the production of conventional cylindrical Type IV tanks. While some of these steps, such as strut bonding, trimming, and forming, could be automated and parallelized (e.g. using a heated press tool for simultaneous forming), the overall production effort and associated costs are high. The cost-effectiveness of these additional manufacturing steps relative to the reported 5-10% increase in volumetric efficiency for cuboid packaging spaces, as indicated by Ruf [16], needs to be further assessed.

6 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

This work presents the development and manufacturing of conformable CFRP tank demonstrators reinforced with continuous fiber-reinforced tension struts. While the integration of struts was successfully demonstrated, key challenges remain in improving compaction in laminate regions without curvature, as well as achieving a reliable interface between the CFRP and the aluminum boss. The two demonstrators showed leakage before burst at 30 and 80 bar, respectively. The manual and labor-intensive forming process of the strut ends shows that this approach is significantly more complex and time-consuming compared to the manufacturing of conventional cylindrical tanks. Future efforts will focus on increasing the strut-wall connection strength, enhancing compaction e.g. through a modified process sequence, and generating concepts for scalable, cost-effective production techniques.

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